

**Summary
of the study's material:**

**Supplementary Material for Comparative Analysis of Data Protection Laws
and Privacy Frameworks: Optimizing Solutions for Compliance with LGPD
and International Data Sharing Laws**

1. Systematic Literature Review (SLR)
 - 1.1. Accepted Studies
 - 1.2. Extraction
 - 1.3. Studies ID (Ref. number)
 - 1.4. RQ Results

2. Survey (Challenges)
 - 2.1. Questions
 - 2.2. Forms Copy
 - 2.3. Responses
 - 2.4. Demographic Results
 - 2.5. Challenges Results

3. Framework Analysis
 - 3.1. Comparative Analysis
 - 3.2. Principles
 - 3.3. Rights

4. Guide
 - 4.1. Questions
 - 4.2. Forms Copy
 - 4.3. Responses
 - 4.4. Graphical Results
 - 4.5. Transcript Results